

Paediatric Palliative and Bereavement Care Beyond Illness - Covering and Caring for Hearts

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Pedraza, E.C., Raguindin, P.F., Hendriks, M.J., Vokinger, A.K., De Clercq, E., Rüesch, K., Hjorth, L., von Bueren, A.O., Tinner, E.M., Bergstraesser, E., Wiener, L., Michel, G. (2023). Palliative care services in paediatric oncology centres across Europe: A cross-sectional survey. *European Journal of Cancer: Paediatric Oncology*, (2); 100125. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ejcped.2023.100125>

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presented by
Eddy Carolina Pedraza Salcedo
19-454-057
From Sogamoso, Colombia
Lucerne, 2024

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First Reviewer: Prof. Dr. Gisela Michel
Second Reviewer: Prof. Dr. Sara Rubinelli
Co-promoters: Dr. phil. Eva De Clercq – Dr. sc. med. Manya Hendriks
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Abstract

Improving the quality of life and reducing suffering for patients and families facing life-limiting or life-threatening illnesses is an ethical duty of HCPs and a moral responsibility of healthcare systems. Early integration of paediatric palliative care and bereavement care for families who lose their children is essential. Further research is required to investigate the global availability of paediatric palliative care, including bereavement care, for children with cancer and other life-limiting illnesses.

The cumulative thesis comprises three separate studies that focus on paediatric palliative and bereavement care for parents and families in the context of childhood cancer and other life-threatening or life-limiting illnesses. The first paper discusses the availability of paediatric palliative care services, including bereavement care in paediatric oncology centres throughout Europe. It also examines the barriers and facilitators healthcare providers perceive when providing palliative care in their centres. The second paper presents a systematic review of hospital-based bereavement programmes and interventions that are offered to bereaved parents in low-middle income countries. The third paper outlines coping strategies adopted by families who have lost a child to childhood cancer, and factors that might influence them in adopting coping mechanisms.

The three studies provide new insights into the field of paediatric palliative care, with a focus on bereavement care. The results are thoroughly discussed and could serve as a basis for future research and implementation in clinical practice.

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First, I would like to thank God for giving me the wonderful opportunity to be part of this amazing project and the privilege of spending these last four years in such a beautiful country. My heart is filled with gratitude for the extraordinary people I had the privilege to meet, people full of love and dedication for what they do.

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Many thanks to Prof. Dr. Sara Rubinelli for kindly agreeing to review the work presented here. It is an honour to have her as part of my thesis committee; her ample experience in communication and leadership in palliative care at the University of Lucerne are admirable. Your constructive criticism will undoubtedly contribute to this work.

I would like to thank my bereavement research team for their unconditional support. I am very glad that we have been growing. I sincerely thank Dr. Manya Hendriks, who guided me during my first years as a Ph.D. candidate, strengthened my character in the professional and research area, and later became an invaluable friend. Endless thanks to Dr. Eva De Clercq for her tremendous support, academic experience, and emotional strength; she encouraged me to continually move towards the goal. Thanks to Dr. Peter Raguidin for his dedication, effort, enthusiasm, and variety of knowledge in research; his professionalism made statistical data analysis part of me as a researcher! Words are not enough to thank my dear colleague, Anna Katherina Vokinger; thank you for dreaming together of the marvellous things coming for the future well-being of children and families needing palliative and bereavement care.

Many, many thanks to my entire work team (Childhood Cancer Research UniLu Team). Each one of them filled my days with new experiences and enriching knowledge; more than coworkers, they became my family in Switzerland. I learned from their strengths, talents, and qualities. There are many

names that I would like to write here, but the paragraph would become too long; however, I can assure that their names are already printed in my heart.

My special thanks to the prestigious University of Lucerne and its Faculty of Health Sciences and Medicine, who opened their doors for my training. Since I arrived in 2019, I have seen it grow, and I am extremely proud to be part of an emerging faculty full of motivation and great vision. Thanks to the cantonal hospitals and their healthcare providers who were part of our project and were always willing to collaborate with our research. I would also like to give special thanks to Dr. Eva Bergsträsser and Eva Maria Tinner for their commitment and advice throughout the study, as well as the other co-authors of the studies.

My most sincere gratitude to Dr. Michael McNeil, Dr. Ximena Garcia, and Dr. Justin Baker, who, through St Jude Global Palliative Care Medicine, allowed me to spend an unforgettable time as a clinical and research observer under their mentorship. There, at St. Jude Research Children's Hospital, I had the opportunity to interact with patients and families and to focus on creating opportunities for this vulnerable population. During this time, I confirmed that it is possible to put into practice what we, as researchers, have developed from theory through analysis, databases, and results. Each mentor's love, compassion, and dedication in their daily work has been and continues to inspire me personally and professionally. Teamwork" is the key that I emphasise here that makes things possible, and dreams come true.

I am highly grateful to SSPH + (Swiss School of Public Health) and its Global PhD Fellowship Program in Public Health Sciences (Global 3PHS) funded by Marie Skłodowska-Curie Actions (Horizon2020-COFUND). Thanks to the grant agreement N° 801076 and their support, what was just an idea turned into reality. Special thanks also go to the other co-founders who were part of the study and each of the publications.

I would also like to take the time to give infinite thanks to my family, my treasure here on earth. My father, mother, siblings, and all my family members, who, despite the distance, have filled my days with faith and hope. With this thesis, I would like to honour my daddy, who always saw me flying high and continues to see me from Heaven. Today, my daddy is not present on this earth; he had to leave just a few months ago, but he will forever remain in my heart, teaching me the reality of grief, a topic still to be discovered. My dad gave my research a tangible meaning and purpose, a sense that bereaved people need active support, love, and kindness; that bereaved people need individuals around (family, friends, community, health workers), who can shelter them and even in silence, just by their presence, give the warmth of compassion. Thank you to my friends and colleagues, to my

home country, Colombia, and to my second home country, Switzerland, for your constant support. Above all, I want to thank God once again for being the Light, the Strength and the Engine that drives my existence.

This thesis could be based on the endless gratitude that wells up from my soul to everyone who has sown a seed in my life. It is my sincere hope that this thesis will touch the heart of each reader, that it will motivate them and make them burn with the desire to support and embrace in love and compassion every child facing life-threatening/limiting illnesses and those in grief (parents, siblings, grandparents, entire family), who have had to face the difficult loss of a loved one.

Finally, I would like to thank the little Carolina that lives inside me, for allowing herself to learn and delve deeper into such an important subject, for loving paediatric palliative care with her heart, for insisting that we are here not just to cure a disease, but to look beyond the diagnosis and find hearts in pain that need to be treated with compassion. For always proclaiming that we are all privileged to serve others through our professions, “that one small act of kindness and love in the right place, at the right time can change and impact thousands of lives”, and for always believing that THERE IS A WAY.

Until then, there are three things that remain: faith, hope, and love-- yet love (compassion) surpasses them all.

1 Corinthians 13:13, TPT version.

List of Abbreviations

EoL: End of Life

HCPs: Healthcare Providers

HICs: High-Income Countries

ICCS-3: International Classification of Childhood Cancer

LMICs: Low-and Middle-Income Countries

PC: Palliative Care

PPC: Paediatric Palliative Care

HIV: Human Immunodeficiency Virus

Contributions

The initiative for this project arose from a dialogue between Prof. Dr. Gisela Michel and one of her colleagues, a paediatric oncologist. Prof. Michel, with over 15 years of research experience in the field of psycho-oncology, has concentrated her investigations on the psychosocial outcomes of children diagnosed with cancer and their families, both during and after treatment and particularly during the survival phase. During their conversation, the question arose, «What about the families of children who unfortunately do not survive? This question remained with Prof. Dr. Michel and eventually became the research question of the overall study, of which this thesis is part. Thus, together with Prof. Michel, Dr. Manya Hendriks and I collaborated on the initial proposal, development, and subsequent sub-studies.

Prof. Dr. Gisela Michel has been supervising the entire project under her affiliation with the University of Lucerne. The original proposal, written by Prof. Michel, Dr. Hendriks, and Eddy Carolina Pedraza, received a 50% grant from the Global PhD Fellowship Program in Public Health Sciences (Global 3PHS), under the auspices of the Swiss School of Public Health (SSPH+), funded by Marie Skłodowska-Curie Actions (Horizon2020-COFUND), grant agreement n° 801076. After that, Prof. Dr. Eva Bergstässer and Dr. med. Eva Maria Tinner approved the first proposal and were co-applicants for a second grant awarded by the Swiss Cancer Research (Grant no. KFS-4995-02-2020). All applicants were part of the preparation for approval by the Ethics Committee in the country. This marked the start of the overall project. Subsequently, new colleagues have joined the team, and their contributions to the sub-studies and published papers are detailed below.

Here, I describe the contributions of my co-authors and me for each paper. The publications listed here appear in the same order as in the thesis.

Pedraza, E.C., Raguindin, P.F., Hendriks, M.J., Vokinger, A.K., De Clercq, E., Rüesch, K., Hjorth, L., von Bueren, A.O., Tinner, E.M., Bergstraesser, E., Wiener, L., Michel, G. (2023). Palliative care services in paediatric oncology centres across Europe: A cross-sectional survey. *European Journal of Cancer: Paediatric Oncology*, (2); 100125. doi.org/10.1016/j.ejcped.2023.100125. ECP, MJH, GM, LH, and LW initiated the study (conceptualization). ECP, MJH, and GM collected the data (methodology, software, resources, data curation). ECP, KR & PFR analysed the data (validation, formal analysis, investigation, data curation). ECP, AKV, PFR, EDC & GM wrote the first draft (writing original draft, visualization). MJH, KR, LH, AOvB, EMT, EB & LW, provided critical inputs on the manuscript (writing, review, and editing). GM supervised the conduct of the study (supervision, project administration). Acquisition of

the financial support for the project leading to this publication: ECP, GM, LW (Funding). All authors approve the final version of the manuscript.

Pedraza, E.C., Vokinger, A.K., Cleves, D., Michel, G., Wrigley, J., Baker, J.N., Garcia-Quintero, X., McNeil, M.J. Bereavement Support for Parents after the Death of a Child in Low- or Middle-Income Countries: a Systematic Review. *Accepted by Journal of Pain and Symptom Management. Under review.* ECP, MM & XG conceptualized and designed the study. ECP, MM, XG, DC, AKV & JW. worked and coordinated the searches, collection, and analysing the data, drafted the initial manuscript, and reviewed and critically reviewed the final version of the manuscript. JB & GM critically revised and edited the manuscript, giving significant feedback on it. All authors approved the final manuscript and agreed to be accountable for all aspects of the work.

Pedraza, E. C., Michel, G., Altherr, A., Hendriks, M. J., & De Clercq, E. (2023). Coping strategies in families who lost a child to cancer: A Scoping review. *European Journal of Cancer: Paediatric Oncology*, (1), 100011. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ejcped.2023.100011>. ECP, GM, MJH & EDC conceptualized and designed the study, worked and coordinated on data collection, coding, and analysis of the data, drafted the initial manuscript, and reviewed and critically revised the final version of the manuscript. AA collaborated with the search, screening, and coding. All authors approved the final manuscript and agreed to be accountable for all aspects of the work.

Extended Summary

Paediatric palliative care (PPC) aims to improve children's and families' quality of life and to alleviate suffering when a child is diagnosed with life-threatening and life-limiting diseases. Palliative care should thus be available as soon as a diagnosis is reached, regardless of the prognosis. Moreover, PPC encompasses the care of children and families at all stages of the disease trajectory, including the bereaved phase, as proposed by WHO guidelines.

The death of a loved one, especially a child, is considered one of the most distressing experiences a family may face. In certain European nations, including Switzerland, up to 15-20% of children may die from cancer, meaning that one in five children may succumb to the disease. Unfortunately, child mortality rates in other parts of the world are even higher, not only due to cancer but also other causes. This thesis aims to provide new insights and knowledge into the availability of current palliative care services, with a focus on bereavement care provided to parents and families who have lost their children to cancer, other childhood illnesses, or other causes of death, and to describe the coping strategies adopted by these bereaved families. This work was performed by exploring palliative and bereavement care services or interventions provided in Europe and low-middle-income countries (LMICs) in specific settings and understanding bereaved families' coping strategies while facing this experience.

To achieve the main objective, we employed various research methods. These included a quantitative cross-sectional survey among healthcare providers (HCPs) working in European paediatric oncology centres. Additionally, we conducted a systematic and a scoping review to explore and identify bereavement programmes and interventions offered in LMICs, as well as the coping strategies that bereaved families may adopt after the loss of their child. This dissertation is part of an ongoing study that investigates the needs and desires of bereaved parents for care following the death of their child. However, the present work does not delve into this specific topic in depth.

The current dissertation consists of four main sections: Introduction (Chapter 1), Methods (Chapter 2), peer-reviewed journal articles (Chapters 3-5), and general discussion (Chapter 6).

Chapter One introduces the context of childhood cancer, other life-limiting/threatening diseases, and PPC. It describes their relationship and the benefits of early integration of PPC to patients and their families. The chapter also provides an overview of the context of high-income countries (HICs) and low-and middle-income countries (LMICs) in relation to PPC. Finally, it focuses on the benefits of

bereavement care for parents and families who have lost their child. Chapter Two provides a summary of the methods used to conduct each study, and how these methods were performed.

The following chapters (3-5) present the individual peer-reviewed articles. Chapter 3 presents a quantitative study (cross-sectional survey) that aims to describe the availability of PPC, including bereavement services in paediatric oncology centres across Europe, and identify barriers and facilitators to implementing and providing PPC. The results revealed that an important percentage of centres provide PC to their patients and families; however, only half of the paediatric oncology centres provided bereavement services to families that have lost their child. Our study concluded that there is a need to strengthen and increase the availability of paediatric palliative and bereavement care, mainly through education, stakeholder support and awareness.

Chapter 4 is based on a systematic review that focused on bereavement services for parents in LMIC. After a thorough methodological process using the PRISMA guidelines, the review included nine articles, of which only 1 described an established bereavement programme. In contrast, others focused on isolated interventions, mainly for mothers who had experienced perinatal (prenatal/neonatal) child loss. The review highlights the need for further research and implementation in the field of bereavement support in LMICs for bereaved families (including parents and other family members).

Finally, Chapter 5 is a scoping review that aimed to synthesise the empirical evidence on coping strategies following the loss of a child to cancer. Specifically, it aimed to describe the coping strategies of different family members (i.e., parents, siblings and grandparents) and to identify the factors that influence these coping strategies. Following a detailed analysis of content and themes, bereaved families adopted five main categories of coping strategies: continuing bonds, making meaning, emotional expression, distraction and refocusing, and finally, caring for others. Our study concluded that there are a variety of coping strategies that each family member may adopt during grief, and that may change over time. This suggests that bereavement is a unique and personal journey, meaning that there is no ideal coping style. Based on our findings, our paper proposed that HCPs could offer more effective support by understanding the coping strategies that the bereaved family members might adopt.

The final chapter (6) provides a general discussion integrating the three papers. This chapter also includes the limitations, strengths, and clinical implications suggested by our findings. Lastly, general and specific conclusions are drawn at the end of the chapter.

Chapter 1: Introduction

This initial chapter aims to offer the readers a comprehensive overview of paediatric palliative care, childhood cancer, and other life-limiting/threatening diseases in a worldwide context, with a particular emphasis on bereavement following the loss of a child.

Paediatric Palliative Care

“I am a 13-year-old boy. I am dying. I write this to you who are and will become nurses and doctors in the hope that, by sharing my feelings with you, you may someday be better able to help those who share my experience. But no one likes to talk about such things. . .The dying person is not yet seen as a person and thus cannot be communicated with as such. He is a symbol of what every human fears and what we each know. [...] Don’t run away. Wait. All I want to know is that someone will hold my hand when I need it. I’m afraid.”

Citation extracted from Siks et al.’s publication¹, describing a beautiful example of what paediatric palliative care really means to a patient, published in 1977 by *Paediatrician’s Manual*.

Paediatric palliative care (PPC) has been an emerging and growing specialty over the last decades.¹ Its main aim is to reduce suffering and improve the quality of life of patients facing life-limiting or life-threatening illness², based on patient- and family-centred care principles.^{2,3}

The term “palliative” has its origins in the Latin word “pallium”, which means “to cloak”.⁴ This term conveys the idea of “covering” or “protecting” the patient who is experiencing suffering or pain. The history of palliative care (PC) dates back many years, when it was originally used in United Kingdom for adult patients who required end-of-life (EoL) care and were admitted into hospices.^{4,5} Prior to the 1990s, the terms 'palliative care' and 'hospice' were used interchangeably.⁶ Therefore, over time, the term PC came to be associated only with EoL care for patients, families, and communities, as well as healthcare providers (HCPs). Thus, it had become stigmatised as a term primarily linked to a forbidden/taboo message about death.^{4,7} Until the World Health Organisation (WHO) provided a conceptual distinction between the two terms, and in the following years, other international organisations and experts adopted the new concepts.⁶ However, prior to this occurrence, additional events in the history occurred.

In the 1970s, Dr Saunders introduced the concept of hospice and 'total pain' in adult care, which encompassed not only physical pain but also psychological, social, and spiritual components of patient care. This concept was echoed in paediatrics, leading to the emergence of the concept of 'total care', which emphasised the physical and emotional care of children as the first steps for PPC. In 1983, experts recommended applying these principles to all ill children, not just those who were dying. The focus should have not only be on childhood cancer but also on other non-oncological diseases. The philosophy had expanded to include the care of the entire family, not just the sick child.¹ Accordingly, to date, palliative care, particularly paediatric palliative care, focuses on caring for patients with life-threatening or life-limiting illnesses, not only at the terminal stage (Figure 1) but the whole trajectory of the disease and also covers the suffering of family members.^{1,7,8}

Figure 1: Timeline of concepts in paediatric palliative care literature. It was adapted from Siks et al.,2020¹.

Hence, PC has been defined by the WHO as “an approach that improves the quality of life of patients (adults and children) and their families who are facing the problems associated with life-threatening illness, through the prevention and relief of suffering by means of early identification and correct assessment and treatment of pain and other problems, whether physical, psychosocial or spiritual”.⁹ Specifically to PPC, since 1998, the definition from the WHO highlights “the active total care of the child’s body, mind and spirit, and also involves giving support to the family”.¹⁰ Thus, PPC could be represented as an *umbrella term* encompassing and including the patient, their families, and the community (Figure 2). It must be available throughout the course of the illness, including at (or before) diagnosis, and should be offered in combination with curative treatment regardless of prognosis.

Additionally, it should provide end-of-life and bereavement care as necessary, in accordance with guidelines of the WHO and other international organisations.^{2,9,11-13}

Figure 2: Schematic diagram of paediatric palliative care (PPC). The umbrella represents the continuum of care for the child and the whole family, providing holistic care (physical, psychological, social, and spiritual). From diagnosis (DX), throughout the course of the disease and even after death.

Recent studies have estimated that over 21 million children worldwide need access to PC each year,^{14,15} of whom more than 8 million would require some level of specialised PPC, i.e., care provided by HCPs specifically trained in PC (given the complexity of patient and family care); however, the numbers vary from country to country.¹⁴ Furthermore, this number is expected to increase in the coming years, as children are more resilient to diseases, and technological improvements have increased the survival rates of children with severe pathologies, allowing them to live longer but with the suffering of chronic symptoms.¹⁶⁻¹⁸

In paediatrics, a variety of pathologies and conditions can be classified as life-limiting or life-threatening (Table 1).^{11,12,14-16} The multiple and broad range of these diseases and the duration of care differs from one to another and is difficult to predict.¹⁶ Accordingly, PPC is predominantly required for genetic, neurological, cardiovascular, neonatal, or oncological conditions.¹⁴ However, also other conditions demand the need for PPC, such as infectious diseases like tuberculosis or HIV (human

immunodeficiency virus).^{12,14,16} While, as mentioned above, the primary objective of PPC is to alleviate suffering and enhance the well-being of patients and their families, it is crucial to provide disease-specific care tailored to the child's needs. Hence, PPC recognises that the nature of each disease, including its symptoms, treatments, decision-making, and advanced care planning, can significantly differ from one to another. For this reason, knowledge of palliative care principles is crucial in any paediatric sub-specialty.

Table 1: Life-limiting and life-threatening diseases in paediatrics. Adapted from^{12,14,16}

Categories	Definition	Examples
Group 1	Life-threatening illness conditions for which curative treatment may be feasible but may fail.	Cancer, organ failure of heart, liver or kidney, infections.
Group 2	Conditions requiring long periods of intensive treatment aiming at prolonging life, but where premature death is still possible.	Cystic fibrosis, Duchene Muscular dystrophy, HIV/AIDS, cardiovascular abnormalities, extreme prematurity.
Group 3	Progressive condition without curative options, where treatment is palliative after diagnosis	Neuromuscular or neurodegenerative disorders, progressive metabolic disorders, chromosomal abnormalities, advanced metastatic cancer on first presentation.
Group 4	Irreversible but non-progressive conditions with severe disability, causing extreme vulnerability to health complications	Severe cerebral palsy, genetic disorders, congenital malformations, prematurity, brain, or spinal cord injury.
Group 5	Very ill neonates at the end-of-life should also be considered as candidates for palliative or comfort care.	

PPC can be provided at multiple levels of care.^{2,8} Not all children and adolescents require a specialised PPC team, and other HCPs (general practitioners, paediatricians, nurses, etc.) may be the first contact in caring for these children to meet their needs.^{8,14} Nevertheless, it is crucial to recognise that various

symptoms associated with these pathologies may require more complex management. It is then essential to be aware when support from specialised PPC teams is needed, as they focus not only on the physical but also on the holistic care (social, psychological, and spiritual suffering) of the child and family.⁸

Furthermore, PC has been shown to improve the quality of life of patients and their families.^{19,20} Reducing hospitalisation rates and, therefore, lowering economic costs.^{19,20} In addition, outcomes are similar for those receiving PPC home-based programmes,²¹ being an effective way of supporting health services and the public health system in general.

This thesis is based on the principles of paediatric palliative care,¹⁷ which encompasses holistic care for not just patients (children and adolescents), but also for their parents, siblings, and even other members of the family, considering all types of distress they may face, including moral distress,²²⁻²⁴ during and after the course of a life limiting/threatening disease.

Overview of Cancers in Childhood

The importance of paediatric palliative care is becoming increasingly recognized in the field of childhood cancer. Childhood cancer is, in fact, still the second highest cause of death for children globally, after accidents in children over one-year-old in high income countries (HICs).^{25,26} In the following paragraphs, I will provide an overview of paediatric oncology and its connection to paediatric palliative care.

“Watching your child suffer the horrors of treatment in order to have a chance at life is something no parent should ever have to experience”

Kristin

10 Quotes from Parents About the Importance of Children’s Cancer Research (curesearch.org)

Childhood cancer is considered a life-threatening condition.^{11,12,16} Worldwide, approximately 400.000 children aged between 0-14 years are diagnosed with childhood cancer annually.²⁷ The incidence rates for childhood cancer differ across countries and continents.²⁷ These variations can be attributed to numerous factors, such as the disease’s nature, which may include both genetic and environmental factors,²⁸ as well as discrepancies in disease reporting and follow-up.²⁷ In Europe, the incidence rate for new cases per million averages between 140-160 children and adolescents, ranging from 103 to over 230 cases/million between nations.²⁹ Comparable incidence rates to the average are observed in

high-income countries (HICs), such as Switzerland.^{30,31} However, even though the fact that 80% of childhood cancer occurs in low-and-middle-income countries (LMIC),²⁷ underreporting in these areas remains a significant concern.

Regardless of the factors mentioned above, as mentioned by Benini, et al. “the clinical and natural history of the disease is different according to the type of cancer”.³² The latest international classification of childhood cancer (ICCC-3) groups the different types of childhood cancer into 12 distinct clusters, each with specific tumour behaviours and treatments (see Table 2).³³

Table 2: international classification of childhood cancer (ICCC-3). Adopted from Steliarova-Foucher E, et al., 2005.³³

<i>Code</i>	<i>Diagnosis</i>
<i>I.</i>	Leukaemias, myeloproliferative diseases, and myelodysplastic diseases
<i>II.</i>	Lymphomas and reticuloendothelial neoplasms
<i>III.</i>	Central nervous system neoplasms
<i>IV.</i>	Neuroblastomas and other peripheral nervous cell tumours
<i>V.</i>	Retinoblastomas
<i>VI.</i>	Renal tumours
<i>VII.</i>	Hepatic tumours
<i>VIII.</i>	Malignant bone tumours
<i>IX.</i>	Soft tissue and other extraosseous sarcomas
<i>X.</i>	Germ cell tumours, trophoblastic tumours, and neoplasms of gonads
<i>XI.</i>	Other malignant epithelial neoplasms and malignant melanomas
<i>XII.</i>	Other specified and unspecified neoplasms
	Langerhans Cell Histiocytosis

Despite significant advances in paediatric oncology and substantial improvements in 5-year survival rates, approximately 20% of children in HICs still die from overall childhood cancer, with higher rates depending on the type of cancer, such as brain tumours.^{31,34}

A bridge between paediatric oncology and paediatric palliative care

While PPC aims at improving the quality of life and reducing suffering for both patients and their families, irrespective of the prognosis; paediatric oncology seeks mainly to offer curative treatment to children and adolescents diagnosed with cancer. Nonetheless, it is important to note that both subspecialties target to adopt a holistic approach to patient care.

“When we began this journey with Audrey we met other families, 13 in fact, whose children had cancer. Today, only three of those kids are alive. Again, we need more funding because those children’s lives mattered, and the children who have come after them matter.”

Krista

10 Quotes from Parents About the Importance of Children’s Cancer Research (curesearch.org)

For many years, it has been known that children and adolescents who receive a cancer diagnosis and their families experience varying degrees of stress, anxiety, depression, and lower scores on quality of life scales.³⁵⁻³⁹ Accordingly, childhood cancer diagnosis impacts the entire family, including its internal functioning.^{36,37,40} Various coping strategies are adopted by family members and patients to overcome the current distress,^{38,41} and standards of psychosocial care for parents and children have been published and implemented lately to support them.^{39,42,43} Nevertheless, the uncertain prognosis for the future may lead to a range of uneasy emotions that can fluctuate from hope, such as a complete cure, to despair, such as the possibility of loss for all of them. (Figure 3).⁴⁴

Figure 3: The trajectory of paediatric cancer: all the possible events and uncertainty about outcome justifies the early integration of paediatric oncology–paediatric palliative care. The disease affects not just the child or young person but the whole family system. Survivors of paediatric cancer endure a number of more or less severe chronic sequelae, and face several adult life challenges, including vocational ones. Adapted from Lacerda et.al, 2023⁴⁴

Paediatric oncology practice usually offers psychological and emotional support to children with cancer and their families through psycho-oncology interventions, but since a cure is the primary goal, approaches and discussions beyond prognosis and the possibility of no cure might be frequently overlooked. While children with cancer and their parents receive substantial support from their oncology treatment team, some parents hold unfavourable perceptions regarding the quality of the information provided about their child's future and prognosis.⁴⁵ Thus, as described by Kaasa et al. (Figure 4),⁴⁶ an early palliative care approach is currently being promoted, with a difference between traditional and modern concepts, where the timing of the introduction of PPC and its concepts to the patients and families are important.

Figure 4. Traditional versus early palliative care. Model based on time of introduction for PPC. Adapted from Kaasa et al., 2018⁴⁶

A new field of paediatric palliative oncology has been proposed, to help children diagnosed with cancer and their families cope with the hopes and uncertainties they face, starting as early as possible and continuing throughout the course of the illness and beyond.^{47,48} Ensuring excellent communication with patients and families is a crucial aspect of integrated care, and here is where PPC lends support to primary oncology care teams.⁴⁷ Other fundamental tenets of PPC, such as symptom control, shared decision-making, advance care planning, and family support (including bereavement care), also become part of the thorough care^{17,47} founded upon interdisciplinary team collaboration.⁴⁷ Hence, paediatric palliative oncology care encompasses comprehensive care, incorporating the four physical, psychological, social, and spiritual dimensions of palliative care for children with cancer and their families.⁴⁷ This emphasizes that pain and suffering are not solely limited to a physical level but have multifaceted components that must be considered.

Early provision of palliative care has been shown to lead to better outcomes during the end-of-life and bereavement stages for families.^{32,47,49} Furthermore, specialized palliative care provided at the hospital or home has been linked with positive results for children with serious medical conditions perceived by patients, parents, and healthcare providers, including improved quality of life.⁵⁰⁻⁵⁴ A systematic review conducted in 2020 reaffirms the potential positive impact of specialist palliative care in paediatric oncology on symptom burden, pain control and quality of life of children, as well as improving family satisfaction and perceptions about communication skills.⁵⁵ Thus, the collaboration between PPC care and paediatric oncology is essential to offer a wide array of support options that are tailored to the needs and preferences of the child and their family (Figure 5).⁴⁴

Figure 5: Expanding the focus of care for children and young people with cancer and their families with the integration of paediatric oncology and paediatric palliative care. Adapted from Lacerda, et.al, 2023.⁴⁴

In a recent publication, Lacerda et al. outline various models that could promote the integration of PPC into paediatric oncology, including the “integrated care model”, in which teams work together from the diagnosis,⁵⁶ as demonstrated in Figure 6.⁴⁴ However, the authors note that early integration of palliative care into paediatric oncology may present certain challenges.⁴⁴ Nevertheless, it is vital to raise awareness of the topic, educate the community (including patients and families), and reinforce the training for healthcare providers to ensure optimal care in all possible treatment scenarios.⁴⁴ Other models of care have also been proposed with similar aims of care,^{8,46-48,56-58} and a new training model for this specific field is currently available in North America.⁵⁹

Figure 6: Possible models of paediatric palliative care delivery in paediatric oncology. Adapted from Lacerda, et.al, 2023. ⁴⁴

Paediatric Palliative Care in High and Low-Middle Income Countries

Despite the gradual growth of paediatric palliative care and its acceptance into paediatric oncology, it is essential that we continue to promote the integration of PPC into other paediatric disciplines in high- and low-income countries. This is particularly relevant as the number of life-limiting and life-threatening diseases in paediatrics in general is increasing worldwide. In this section, I will provide a brief overview of this and its potential challenges.

“Please be patient with me. Sometimes when I’m quiet, it’s because I need to figure myself out. It’s not because I don’t want to talk. Sometimes there are no words for my thoughts.”
Kamla Bolanos

227 Chronic Illness Quotes For Coping & Peace (2023) (everydaypower.com)

While much of the progress in PC and childhood cancer has taken place in high-income countries (HICs), as noted above, a large proportion of children and adolescents in need of PC are in low- and middle-income countries (LMICs), as illustrated in Figure 7.⁹ Thus, for example, approximately 80-90% of childhood cancer diagnoses occur in LMICs, where survival rates are much lower than in HICs.^{27,60-63} The estimated number of children aged 0 to 19 years who required palliative care globally in 2017 was almost 4 million,⁹ with this number expected to increase in the coming years.¹⁴ Thus, more than 97% of children in need of PPC live in LMICs,⁹ recognising that childhood cancer is not the only diagnosis that triggers this need (Figure 8). Reports also indicate a shortage of palliative care programmes and limited access in LMICs,^{9,64} although there is hope in the ongoing work being done.⁶⁰

Figure 7: Worldwide need for palliative care for children (0-19) by income group (183 countries; 2017). Adapted from Connor et al., 2020⁹

As highlighted earlier in this chapter, PPC must be made available for all life-threatening or life-limiting illnesses, including those related to cardiology, neurology, genetics, or other paediatric subspecialties,⁹ as Sisk et al. have referred in their publication, “paediatric palliative care is now a philosophy of care that transcends any particular subspecialty”.¹ Thus, the umbrella of paediatric palliative care becomes wider to all children and family in need. (Figure 8).

Figure 8: Worldwide need for palliative care for children by disease groups (0-19 years; 2017). Adapted from Connor et al., 2020⁹

Ensuring palliative care for patients in both low- and high-income countries presents many challenges. Barriers to palliative care may arise from various sources, including parents' and families' perceptions,⁶⁵ as well as healthcare professionals' lack of awareness and understanding of palliative care.⁶⁶ Furthermore, both low- and high-income countries commonly face a shortage of skilled

personnel, time, and resources. However, it seems that LMICs experience greater disparities due to the lack of funding and government and health system support.⁶⁷ Further research is necessary in both settings to provide appropriate support for each population, taking into account their needs, preferences, and cultural backgrounds.

Bereavement Care for parents and families as integrative part of PPC

Although child mortality rates have decreased worldwide in the last decades, a significant number of children still die.⁶⁸ Hence, bereavement support for parents and other family members is crucial. The following section gives an insight into this topic.

*“Grief is like the ocean; it comes on waves ebbing and flowing.
Sometimes the water is calm, and sometimes it is overwhelming.
All we can do is learn to swim”.*

*Vicki Harrison
Healing Holidays on X*

The loss of a child is acknowledged as one of the most heart-wrenching experiences a parent can undergo,⁶⁹⁻⁷² as it disrupts the natural order of life.⁷² Some parents have metaphorically described their emotions as having a hole in their hearts⁷³ and the grieving process as being covered with a wet and dark blanket that can feel more or less heavy on some days.⁷⁴ The negative outcomes for bereaved parents are numerous and have been described as the risk of developing physical⁷⁵⁻⁷⁷ and psychological⁷⁷⁻⁸⁰ conditions, up to and including psychiatric hospitalisation^{81,82} and increased mortality.⁸³ Besides parents, other family members such as siblings,^{84,85} and grandparents,^{86,87} are also affected by a child’s death.

As for clarity, it would be beneficial to address some definitions such as the distinctions between “bereavement”, “grief” and “mourning”, which are occasionally used synonymously in the literature, and the general community. Bereavement refers to the objective process following the death of a loved one; grief encompasses all emotional reactions to this event, while mourning involves the public expressions of the grief,⁸⁸ that could be related to traditions and customs, which are often heavily influenced by one’s cultural background. Numerous theories on grief expression have emerged in recent decades, encompassing a wide variety of approaches to coping with grief,⁸⁸⁻⁹³ ranging from explanations of grief as “stages” (e.g., Klübler Ross’ 5 stages of grief)⁸⁹ to more recent theories that consider grief as an ongoing “process” (e.g., Stroebe and Schut’s Dual Process Model).^{90,94}

Snaman et al. (2020),⁹⁵ proposed a longitudinal framework for early parental grief (first 2 years of a child's death) based on former theories, previous qualitative research, and extensive clinical experience working with bereaved parents. The framework suggests that pre- and post-death factors (protective and risk ones), including the PPC (team) support present throughout the disease trajectory, may influence the psychosocial outcomes of bereavement on parents and ways of coping. (Figure 9). The authors suggest that HCPs and communities could offer supportive interventions, and future research can be conducted while understanding these factors that might be modifiable.^{95,96} The right approach of looking at modifiable factors may also be beneficial for longer-term outcomes for bereaved families.^{85,97}

Thus, the journey of grief is unique to each family member. Parents who were able to share their problems with others and had counselling from HCPs reported working through their grief in a better way.⁹⁷ Grief encompasses several stages beyond the period immediately following the loss of a loved one. As mentioned above, these range from early (anticipatory) grief, which may begin when the individual is still alive, to the long-term aftermath of the death.⁹⁸ In this manner, PPC holistically incorporates care for families coping with bereavement, even prior before the death of the child.

Bereavement care is an integral part of PPC and has been proposed as a standard of care.^{32,99-101} Despite its growing recognition, bereavement care is not yet implemented in all paediatric institutions, including those caring for children with cancer.^{102,103} However, it is known from the literature that bereaved family members (fathers, mothers, siblings) have expressed the need for the development of more comprehensive bereavement care and follow-up, involving HCPs and the medical institution,^{98,104-106} as they sometimes feel "abandoned" by the treatment unit,¹⁰⁷ grieving not only their child but also their "family", "second home" or community.^{99,108}

Recent literature has noted the emergence and advancement of bereavement care programmes in countries including Australia, the United States and several parts of Europe, although its provision is highly variable.^{104,109-112} However, it appears that such programmes have not yet been developed in LMICs, and interventions for bereaved families are scarce in the literature.

Figure 9: Conceptual framework for understanding, assessing, and studying aspects related to early psychosocial and physical health outcomes in parents of children that died from cancer. This longitudinal model incorporates parental demographic information and physical and psychological premorbidities and functioning and child factors including cancer diagnosis, treatment, and end-of-life care. Parental social integration and functioning is essential to examine and depends on the ongoing oscillation between and potential protective and risk factors in the early (first 2 years) post-death period. Adopted from Snaman et al., 2020.⁹⁵

Although many HCPs are supportive of providing bereavement services to grieving parents, clinical practice shows high discrepancies between professionals and institutions, and barriers as lack of time, resources and training are highlighted.^{105,113} Furthermore, it is yet unclear how much follow-up time should be given to families who have experienced loss.⁹⁸ Although complicated grief,¹¹⁴ is reported only in a small percentage of cases in bereaved individuals, the detrimental effects such as anxiety, depression, and physical disorders on this vulnerable population have been well documented,¹¹⁵ as mentioned earlier in this section. The absence of expertise, formal education, and proficiency in bereavement care results in escalated distress and substandard living conditions among bereaved families.

So, why is bereavement and follow-up care necessary? As discussed above, bereaved families may experience various co-morbidities in different aspects of their lives following their child's death. Adequate support from hospitals, HCPs, and the community is crucial, ensuring that families can adjust, cope, and reintegrate into society appropriately, ultimately promoting their health and well-being. Appropriate follow-up could also help in the early detection of mental or physical disorders. As proposed by Morris et al. (2015) with the concept of bereavement services as a preventive model of care, acknowledging that bereavement care is an integral and essential part of PPC.¹⁰⁰

Research Gaps

Despite the global expansion of PPC and bereavement care, particularly in HICs, research gaps still require attention. This thesis is part of an ongoing study that aims to develop a better understanding of the palliative and bereavement care services provided to families affected by childhood cancer. Therefore, two papers focused on research gaps in this context, specifically bereavement care. However, during my research and clinical placement in the Global Palliative Care Medicine Department at St Jude Research Children's Hospital, I have written a third piece of work that expands the topic to include all life-limiting and life-threatening illnesses in LMICs.

Research Gap 1: Lack of empirical evidence on the availability of PPC services, including bereavement care, in paediatric oncology centres was identified in the literature. Although research had been carried out in other regions of Europe and globally in different contexts and target populations, paediatric oncology centres had not been explored. Furthermore, there was still insufficient information on the perceived barriers and facilitators for healthcare professionals to implement and provide palliative and bereavement care in these specific settings in Europe. As a result, our first paper in Chapter 3 aims to address these gaps.

Research Gap 2: Information on established bereavement programmes and interventions in children's hospitals worldwide to support families who have experienced the loss of a child is still scarce, particularly outside Europe, and North America. Although there is some evidence of an increase in such programmes in high-income countries (HICs) in recent decades, there is a gap in the literature on this topic in low- and middle-income countries (LMICs). **Chapter 4** presents a study that investigated the programmes, services, initiatives, resources, or interventions available in hospitals in LMICs to support parents who have lost a child (aged 0-18 years).

Research Gap 3: In order to provide appropriate support to parents who have lost their children, it is essential to understand their needs, experiences and coping strategies following the death of their child. An in-depth exploration of the coping strategies used by bereaved family members is needed. This understanding will enable HCPs to provide effective and personalised support to each family member and ensure that hospitals provide the necessary resources. Despite the growing body of literature on this topic, there has not yet been a systematic review summarising the coping strategies used not only by parents who have lost a child to cancer, but also by other family members such as siblings and grandparents. **Chapter 5** aimed to address this gap.

Chapter 2: Methods

This thesis employs various methodological approaches to investigate the availability of palliative and bereavement care services for children and families worldwide, as well as the coping strategies employed by bereaved families following the loss of their child. The dissertation uses the following methods in chapters 3, 4, and 5.

Paper 1 (chapter 3): PPC and bereavement care services in the European Paediatric Oncology context.

This part presents the outcomes of a cross-sectional survey that investigates paediatric palliative care (PPC) availability, including bereavement services, in paediatric oncology centres across Europe, including the European Union, the Schengen area, and the British Isles. The methodology employed a quantitative approach. A cross-sectional online questionnaire was adapted from a previous study to the European context. An international panel of experts carried out internal validation before distribution to the different centres. The survey consisted of four domains: (1) the professional profile of healthcare professionals (HCPs), (2) characteristics of cancer centres, (3) communication and decision support for families' needs, and (4) bereavement services. The survey was disseminated between February 2021 and July 2022 and was available in English. It was intended for completion by healthcare professionals (HCPs) with expertise in paediatric palliative care (PPC) or those with the most knowledge in the field at children's oncology centres. The European countries have been categorised into five regions: the British Isles, Northern, Southern, Western and Eastern. Descriptive analysis was conducted using means and percentages, as required. The responses were compared by region using the chi-squared test and ANOVA. Multinomial and multivariate logistic regressions were also performed to evaluate associations.

Paper 2 (chapter 4): Bereavement care beyond Europe, programmes and interventions in LMICs.

As the purpose of the second paper was to identify the programmes, services, initiatives, resources, or interventions available in hospitals in LMICs to support parents who have lost a child (aged 0-18), to achieve this aim, we conducted a systematic review following the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses (PRISMA) guidelines in order to determine institutional programmes or bereavement interventions in this specific setting. LMICs were defined as those countries classified as such by the World Bank in 2022. The study searched six databases using an advanced research strategy without restrictions on publication date or language in the first screening. Papers included qualitative, quantitative, and mixed methods approaches. Additionally, references

were searched for potentially eligible articles. Since we hypothesized that only a limited number of studies would be available, we opted to expand the scope beyond childhood cancer and encompass all forms of bereavement care provided to parents who have lost a child, regardless of the cause, including accidents and other illnesses. The online screening platform Covidence was used for data collection and extraction. Due to the diversity of content and interventions, a meta-analysis was not feasible. Each paper underwent a quality assessment. Moreover, the paper describes how these interventions may impact their psychosocial outcomes.

Paper 3 (chapter 5): Coping strategies adopted by bereaved families after the loss of their loved child.

This paper presents a scoping review describing the coping strategies adopted by various family members, including parents, siblings, and grandparents, and identifying the factors that may influence these strategies. The study was prepared following the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses (PRISMA) guidelines statement. To address our research question comprehensively and include data from all research methodologies, we conducted a scoping review following the systematic steps proposed by Sandelowski and Borroso. We searched five databases using Boolean logic to combine search terms and identified additional papers by checking the reference lists. The study analysed papers written in Dutch, English, Spanish, German, and Italian, which were the languages spoken by the co-authors. Papers that focused on bereavement support interventions were excluded as they are considered external support. Content analysis was used for data analysis. The co-authors discussed and agreed upon a coding system, which was then used to cluster and categorise codes into thematic groups for in-depth analysis.

Chapter 3: PPC and bereavement care services in the European Paediatric Oncology Context.

Palliative care services in paediatric oncology centres across Europe: A cross-sectional survey.

Pedraza, E.C., Raguindin, P.F., Hendriks, M.J., Vokinger, A.K., De Clercq, E., Rüesch, K., Hjorth, L., von Bueren, A.O., Tinner, E.M., Bergstraesser, E., Wiener, L., Michel, G.

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Chapter 4: Bereavement care beyond Europe, programmes and interventions in LMICs.

Grief and Bereavement Support for Parents in Low- or Middle-Income Countries: A Systematic Review

Pedraza, E.C., Vokinger, A.K., Cleves, D., Michel, G., Wrigley, J., Baker, J.N., Garcia-Quintero, X., McNeil, M.J.

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Chapter 5: Coping strategies adopted by bereaved families after the loss of their loved child.

Coping strategies in families who lost a child to cancer: A scoping review

Pedraza, E. C., Michel, G., Altherr, A., Hendriks, M. J., & De Clercq, E.

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CHAPTER 6: General discussion

This chapter presents and synthesises each study's results and contextualises their findings in a comprehensive discussion. The following structure will be adopted: First, an overview of each study's main research goals and overall outcomes will be provided. Afterward, a general discussion that integrates the three papers is given. The conclusions will be placed within a larger perspective. I will conclude this chapter by outlining the research's strengths and limitations and the potential clinical applications for future practice and research.

“The reality is that you will grieve forever. You will not ‘get over’ the loss of a loved one; you will learn to live with it. You will heal and you will rebuild yourself around the loss you have suffered. You will be whole again, but you will never be the same. Nor should you be the same nor would you want to.”

~ Elisabeth Kubler-Ross and David Kessler

Kubler-Ross, D., & Kessler, E. (2014). On grief and grieving. Simon & Schuster.

1. Summary of main findings

1.1. Chapter 3 – Palliative services in Paediatric Oncology across Europe.

Box 1. Objectives of the Study

- To describe the availability of PPC, including bereavement services, in paediatric oncology centres in Europe,
- To identify barriers and facilitators for implementing and providing PPC.

This study's key findings are noteworthy. According to the cross-sectional survey, over half of the paediatric oncology centres provide specialised paediatric palliative care to their patients. However, more than a third of these centres reported that their capacity was lower than their demand.

In addition, HCPs typically introduce PC concepts to patients and families and provide PC at specific points in the disease course, such as when there is disease deterioration (e.g., relapse, refractory disease, or symptom burden management). It is important to note that a new diagnosis of childhood

cancer does not automatically trigger a PPC consultation, which means that although PPC is provided, it does not fully meet international recommendations (WHO)². Only half of the surveyed centres offered bereavement services, and the length of follow-up varied widely. However, most centres provided resources such as counselling, telephone calls, cards, and letters of condolence. HCPs perceive several barriers to providing PPC and bereavement care. These barriers include parents' negative perceptions of palliative care, late referrals, and lack of awareness and understanding of PPC by other colleagues.

1.2 Chapter 4 – Beyond Europe, bereavement Care in Low-and-Middle Income Countries

Box 2. Objectives of the Study

- To systematically review and describe evidence of programmes, services, initiatives, resources, or interventions offered in hospital settings in LMICs to support bereaved parents after the death of a child (0–18 years old).

The systematic review identified a limited number of studies that documented bereavement interventions in LMICs. Of these, only one paper included a bereavement workshop for parents and family members whose child died between the ages of 0 and 18 years old. The remaining eight papers focused on interventions provided to parents, mostly mothers, who lost their child during the antenatal and neonatal period. Out of the nine reviewed papers, only one described an established bereavement programme, while the other eight mainly described isolated interventions. Most of the studies indicated that psychological counselling was effective in improving the psychological well-being of bereaved mothers. Other interventions, such as creating a momentum by taking footprints, photographs, or allowing mothers to see and hug their child after death, were also found to be helpful for their psychological wellbeing.

1.3 Chapter 5 – Coping Strategies Bereavement Families adopt after the loss of a child.

Box 3. Objectives of the Study

To synthesise empirical evidence on coping strategies after losing a child to cancer by:

- Describing the coping strategies of various family members (i.e., parents, siblings, and grandparents).
- Identifying factors that influence those coping strategies.

The scoping review comprised 34 papers. Following a qualitative thematic analysis, we identified five overarching coping strategies: continuing bonds, meaning-making, emotional expressions, distraction and refocusing, and taking care of others. Continuing bonds and meaning-making were the most frequently reported strategies. Parents and siblings often express a desire to maintain a connection with their deceased child through various activities, such as talking about them, keeping their belongings, visiting the grave, and creating memories. Furthermore, many family members reported trying to make sense of the experience and adopting a new attitude of compassion towards others, prioritising their family relationships. It is important to note that grief is an ongoing process without closure, and coping strategies may change over time. This scoping review focuses on the coping strategies of mothers, fathers, and siblings who have lost children to cancer. No papers were found addressing the coping strategies of grandparents or other family members. It should be also highlighted that fathers and young siblings are underrepresented in the literature, based on our findings.

The review indicated that coping mechanisms can be affected by various factors, including parental role, age and developmental needs of siblings, cultural background, and time since the child's death. The findings conclude that grief is a unique journey, and families should be reassured that they can cope as they choose. Thus, our findings provide important insight for HCPs to recognise that bereaved family members may use various strategies. This will enable professionals to provide more effective support to vulnerable families and identify factors that may put this population at risk of physical and psychological distress.

2. Synthesis and discussion of the main findings:

The three studies presented in this thesis offer substantial evidence that was previously unavailable in paediatric palliative and bereavement care. In the following sections, I will discuss the findings in an integrative way.

2.1. Palliative and Bereavement care, caring beyond death.

Bereavement is a complex experience that defies easy explanation. Numerous authors have proposed various theories of grief to aid in comprehending and assisting those who have lost a loved one.^{92,94,116} However, while each theory aims to illuminate how to cope with grief, each person is free to deal with it in their own way,⁹² as grief is personal and distinct. As demonstrated in our third paper, family members (fathers, mothers, siblings) may adopt different strategies of coping after the death of a child.¹¹⁷ Losing a parent, spouse, or friend can be a hurting experience that should be respected.

However, the loss of a child is often described as the most profound and enduring form of grief, particularly for parents.^{69,118}

Parents often describe the loss of a child as a traumatic event that leaves an indescribable hole in their hearts,⁷³ which may last indefinitely. Thus, our third paper also enhances those statements by concluding that grief is unique both in expression and duration. Children are often considered their parents' most precious possession and the reason for their life. In one way or another, their children give meaning to their parenthood, evoking their dreams for the future and unconditional love. Hence, witnessing the suffering, death, and burial of a child is an unexpected and significant challenge, also when it comes to siblings,⁸⁵ grandparents,^{86,87} friends, and other extended family members.

Grief may manifest differently depending on the circumstances of the death, such as sudden accidents versus illness, whether acute or chronic.¹¹⁹ Thus, families of children diagnosed with life-limiting or life-threatening illnesses may face different reactions and experiences when compared to each other.⁹⁸ Many of them may involve grief and sorrow from the moment of diagnosis due to the uncertainty of the outcome and course of the disease, as in the case of childhood cancer; thus, PPC teams can be supportive from this point.^{2,11} Childhood cancer may also bring an ambivalence between hope and despair about possible outcomes regardless of the prognosis.⁴⁴ Our third paper gave us insights into this topic by describing the coping strategies of bereaved families of children with cancer and discussing how they might differ from other causes of death, although there is not much information available that compares these groups. Nevertheless, it is essential to note that all forms of bereavement share the common experience of suffering.

Suffering for both patients and their families is challenging to comprehend objectively. Just as individuals experience grief differently, they also experience pain differently depending on their circumstances. As Cassel and et. al quote "Suffering is experienced by persons, not merely by bodies, and has its source in challenges that threaten the intactness of the person as a complex social and psychological entity",¹²⁰ meaning that the pain/suffering is not limited to physical discomfort, but rather affects all aspects of their lives, including psychological, social, familial, and spiritual areas. As PPC and bereavement care aim to prevent and reduce suffering and improve quality of life during the trajectory of the disease and after death,¹⁰ it must be included as part of the multidisciplinary treatment team.^{11,32} Our first paper on the availability of PPC in European paediatric oncology centres describes an overview of the professions involved in the care of children and families requiring PPC in the surveyed centres, reporting professions such as doctors, nurses, psychologists, chaplains and many others. In addition, our study found that more than half of the centres reported care provided

by multidisciplinary teams. However, there may still be a shortage of professionals involved in bereavement care.

Bereavement care should be offered to all grieving families, both before, 'anticipatory grief', and after death.⁹⁸ To understand the needs of bereaved families, coping strategies are essential. HCPs should be aware of the mechanisms that bereaved parents, siblings, and other family members adopt. With this in mind, our third paper also emphasised the significance of comprehending the adopted coping strategies by this vulnerable population, even before death, recognizing that this understanding would lead to more effective support from the healthcare team, including the development and implementation of appropriate bereavement programmes and interventions.

Chapter five also discusses the need for HCPs to be aware of the possible factors that may influence bereavement and coping with it. HCPs are often the first point of contact between families, patients and the healthcare system and community support.^{121,122} As mentioned above, our study summarises and categorises possible coping strategies for bereaved mothers, fathers and siblings, but also identifies factors that may affect them, such as parental role, age and mental development of siblings, cultural background and time elapsed since the child's death. These factors should be known by all HCPs who care for children and their families, including general practitioners, paediatricians, nurses, etc., and not just some of them, such as psychologists, social workers, or chaplains; in order to provide the best possible holistic care.

As suggested by our study, more research is needed to better understand how the family as a unit and underrepresented family members, such as grandparents, fathers and younger siblings, cope with the death of their child, as mentioned by other authors,¹²³ in an effort to provide them with appropriate support. Finally, allowing bereaved families to present their coping styles and reassuring them that there is no ideal coping strategy may improve bereavement care and communication with bereaved family members in hospital and community settings. However, while acknowledging grief in all its forms and allowing bereaved family members to cope in their own way doesn't absolve HCPs of the responsibility to be vigilant for signs of pathological grief. Thus, understanding the coping strategies that bereaved families use and the different expressions of grief that they may experience can help HCPs to provide more effective support.

2.2 A need for palliative and bereavement care globally.

The lack of support and follow-up for children and families facing life-limiting/threatening diseases¹⁴ or the death of the child is evident worldwide.^{9,14} In Chapter 2 of this thesis we described the availability of palliative care services, including bereavement care, in paediatric oncology centres

across Europe. Moving from general PC to specific bereavement care, our results showed that although a significant number of the oncology centres surveyed provided PC, only half of them offered bereavement programmes for those families who had lost their child, although they still provided individual resources such as psychological counselling, telephone calls, condolence letters. To our knowledge, no study on palliative and bereavement care has been conducted at European level in paediatric oncology centres, although similar studies have been conducted in other regions and target populations.^{66,124-126}

Furthermore, our first study revealed that the timing of follow-up care after a child's death varied widely between centres, which is consistent with the findings of Wiener et al. in the United States.¹⁰² This led us to suggest that there is a lack of standardised bereavement guidelines implemented at both national and international levels. In this regard, bereavement standards of care recommend providing at least one meaningful intervention to families who have lost a loved one in the follow-up, in order to identify the risk of negative psychosocial outcomes.⁹⁹ Our findings suggest that not all paediatric oncology centres adhere to the recommendation of providing bereavement care systematically, which is consistent with similar observations in other regions.¹⁰² In addition, as a point of discussion, a single contact with the bereaved may not be sufficient, so personalised follow-up should be considered, using the bereavement care as prevention model proposed by Morris.¹⁰⁰ The literature confirms the benefits of bereavement support, but unfortunately the frequency and content of this support remains unclear,⁹⁸ more research need to be conducted on the needs and desires of bereaved families.

In our first study, although many participating centres reported that they provided PC, more than a third reported by their perception that demand exceeded their capacity. This finding was more significant in countries with good implementation of PPC services, suggesting that the greater the knowledge and implementation of PC, the greater the awareness of the need for it. In addition, a very low percentage of centres reported initiating PPC at an early stage (new cancer diagnosis), which is consistent with other studies.¹²⁷ In contrast, implementation and communication with patients and families occur at later specific times (e.g., refractory disease, symptom burden, discussion of advanced care planning), which is also supported by other studies.^{66,128}

The findings of our first and second papers support the statement that bereavement care in hospital settings for families who have lost a child is limited, not only in Europe but worldwide. Despite the recent increase in literature, most published papers describe established programmes,^{104,111,112,129} and reviews of interventions offered primarily by HICs,¹³⁰⁻¹³² including those reporting bereavement care for individuals who lost a loved one, not during childhood.¹²¹ However, it is important to note that

most children and adolescents with life-limiting or life-threatening illnesses reside in LMICs.⁹ Additionally, child mortality rates are highest in these regions.¹³³

Therefore, our second paper systematically reviews the literature for bereavement programmes or interventions provided at hospital settings in LMICs. As expected, our findings reveal a concerning lack of published evidence. We propose two possible explanations for this lack of support. The first is based on the hypothesis that if bereavement programmes are lacking in HICs, the number of programmes in LMICs is much smaller, mainly due to a scarcity of funding and resources. The second explanation is that there are limited research and publication opportunities in LMICs, which further contributes to the disparity between the two scenarios (HICs vs LMICs). Regardless of these differences, it is essential to recognise the need for standardised programmes/interventions in all hospitals that care for sick children worldwide.

Why is it important to promote bereavement care worldwide? As discussed in the introduction, bereaved family members, including parents, siblings, and others, are at risk of developing negative outcomes in all areas of their lives, including physical and psychosocial aspects. Morris and colleagues suggest that bereavement counselling and programmes should be adapted as a preventive resource for parents and families who have lost their children,^{100,111} as we also agreed based on the results of our work. Although not all bereaved family members require professional interventions, it is the responsibility of the health system and primary healthcare providers to support these families and to be able to screen who might need special care. Families who have lost their children are particularly affected by the lack of bereavement support, as it marks a new stage of life for them, and guidance should be provided.⁹⁹ Studies have shown that bereaved parents express a need for more comprehensive bereavement care from healthcare providers and medical institutions.^{102,104,106} Furthermore, bereaved families not only experience the loss of their child but also express the loss of their second family, the hospital staff, particularly those who have spent a significant amount of time at the centre.^{107,108,110}

2.3 Bridging Paediatric Palliative Care and Other Paediatric Specialties

Establishing a strong and secure connection between paediatric palliative care and other paediatric specialties is crucial for providing holistic care to children and families. PPC and paediatric oncology provide an excellent example on this regard, that other disciplines should follow. Garcia-Duque and colleagues draw a comparison between the experience of being diagnosed with cancer and a voyage led by a multidisciplinary team (including PPC).¹³⁴ The PPC team leads the boat together with the primary discipline, in this case, oncology, working tirelessly day and night to get the ship to its final

destination.¹³⁴ This analogy emphasises the significance of effective teamwork in cancer care, as well as it also should be in other life-limiting and life-threatening diseases. PPC and other specialties should complement each other in their shared objective of caring for children, adolescents, and their families. Thus, as is also shown in the picture, the PPC should not be seen as a float of last resort (Figure 10).¹³⁴

Furthermore, in the case of a poor prognosis, the whole team should be prepared to support and advise the child and family through the bereavement process as the child reaches EoL and beyond.¹³⁴ PPC then support the primary teams when they are unsure of how to proceed in this respect. As we have emphasised, PPC should always be considered as part of the initial team, regardless of the prognosis of the life-threatening or life-limiting illness. This is because it also affects outcomes in the bereavement phase for families.

Figure 10: (A) Traditional model . (B) Integrative model of PPC. Adopted from Garcia et al., 2023¹³⁴

A bridge should be built and maintained to connect the qualities and strengths of both sides rather than a wall separating them (PPC and other paediatric specialties, e.g., oncology, neonatology, neurology, etc.), for the benefit of all children and families in need of PPC. While progress is being made step by step, more awareness and advocacy are needed to amplify the voices of those who are not yet being heard.

2.4 Barriers and Facilitators

Implementing PPC and bereavement support is a complex challenge. Our first study identified the perceived barriers and facilitators reported by HCPs at their centres, highlighting that parents' negative misconceptions about PPC, late referrals, and the lack of awareness from HCPs were the main barriers. Our findings are similar to those of other studies in HICs and LMICs.^{66,126,128,135} It is crucial to educate patients, families, and the wider community, as well as the HCPs at hospitals, on PPC's true meaning/definition and aims. In this regard, for example, a study conducted by McNeil et al. listed some of the misconceptions about PC mentioned by surveyed HCPs as “(1) palliative care is synonymous with end-of-life care (43.4% of responses were not aligned with WHO guidance), (2) early consultation with palliative care causes increased parental burden and anxiety (36.8% were not aligned), and (3) it is difficult to know when a patient with cancer would most benefit from a consultation with the palliative care team (30.4% were not aligned)”.¹²⁶ Late referral and negative parental perceptions of PC may be related to these perceptions. Our findings reinforce the need to educate and promote a new culture of open discussion about PC in hospital and social/community settings.

Additionally, inadequate funding, training, and other logistical resources also remained significant barriers worldwide, as described in our work. A recent systematic review of reviews focusing on cancer diagnosis in adults describes these challenges in LMICs. It also highlights the poor perception of palliative care among patients, the general population, and HCPs as one of the main barriers, as well as a lack of trained staff. Perhaps in contrast to HICs, this study also points to the poor infrastructure resources, supply of medicines, and lack of national plans as making access to palliative care more difficult for vulnerable populations in LMICs.⁶⁷ Again, awareness, education, finances, and more resources and research are fundamental facilitators, as we conclude in our study and is supported by other researchers.^{67,126,135}

While HCPs are willing to support bereaved families and children who need PPC from an early stage of illness (preferably diagnosis) and recognize its importance,^{126,128} they also need more support from higher levels of decision-making and guidelines. Healthcare systems and policy makers, rather than HCPs individually, should find a way to overcome the barriers and promote facilitators in this area.

Finally, multidisciplinary teamwork should be recognised as a key to providing appropriate PPC and bereavement care. However, it can be seen either as a barrier or a facilitator, depending on the connections established by team members and their ability to work together. Whether or not curative treatment is provided, all HCPs should focus on the common goal of care, quality of life and reduction

of suffering for the child and family. Lack of effective communication between HCPs, can lead to undesirable outcomes. However, proper communication and efficient relationships (, recognising their own roles, and be willing to learn from others) will certainly lead to successful holistic PPC and bereavement care, which will also lead to effective communication desired by patients and families.¹⁰⁶

3. Strengths and Limitations

This thesis has several strengths as well as limitations. In terms of strengths, the primary focus of this work was to provide relevant information in PPC with a focus on bereavement care in a comprehensive way that was not previously available in the literature. Each of the studies was methodologically designed to fulfil its basic purpose of answering the research questions. Our first study provided a broad systematic overview of paediatric palliative care services, including bereavement care, in paediatric oncology centres at a European level. Although other studies have been developed on PPC,^{15,124,125} none of them are specific to this population. In addition, using a validated questionnaire⁶⁶ previously applied in other regions of the world allowed us to compare results objectively. Finally, our work sought to systematically include all participating centres in Europe and reduce respondent bias by inviting HCPs with expertise in PPC at their centres; statistical methods were also used to overcome these challenges (for instance, sensitivity analysis).

To the best of our knowledge, the second and third articles are the first systematic and scoping reviews, respectively, to examine bereavement programmes or interventions offered in LMIC and the coping strategies adopted by bereaved families after the loss of a child. In terms of methodology, a systematic review of the literature was carried out for the two studies, following the PRISMA guidelines. Multiple databases were used, with no time restrictions. In terms of languages for the systematic review, all papers were included in the first screening (title, abstract and full text), none of the full text papers were in a foreign language. Although our scoping excluded papers that were not spoken by co-authors, a wide range of languages were included (English, German, French, Dutch, Italian and Spanish, in order to retrieve as many articles as possible. In addition, a critical appraisal was carried out to assess the quality of the included papers for possible bias in the systematic review.

Furthermore, the present work (including our three publications) is part of an ongoing project. In this regard, our findings provide evidence to support current and future studies in our research team. Thus, for example, a new co-authored paper describes the implementation of bereavement care at hospital level in an LMIC, Colombia (under internal review). Other papers and research are in development to understand the needs and wishes of bereaved parents about how they should be supported after the loss of their children.

However, as mentioned before, there are limitations that need to be elucidated. Focusing on our European cross-sectional survey, a potential self-report bias can be considered as one of the main challenges, as only one HCP per centre was invited to respond to our survey. Nevertheless, in order to reduce this bias, we explicitly requested in our invitation letter that this person should be an expert or have the greatest knowledge about PPC in his/her centre. It is also possible that each HCP may have had a more positive view of their centre than the reality and may have shared their individual perspective rather than the real situation at the centre. Nonetheless, to overcome this, we performed a sensitivity analysis to rule out this bias. In addition, we may also have had a non-response bias, as it is possible that some centres were unwilling to be part of the study due to a lack of knowledge, availability of services, or other reasons. To address this, we also estimated the worst-case scenario regarding PPC availability in Europe, which is described in our publication.

As with the other two studies (systematic review and scoping review), although the database searches were minimally restrictive, it is possible that some papers were not included in our studies. One reason may be that some bereavement programmes, interventions, or research conducted mainly in LMIC countries were not yet published. Another reason may be that some databases used worldwide were not included, especially those focused on a particular language or regions. In addition, our studies focus on paediatrics; therefore, the population older than 18 years was excluded from our scope. Finally, as this is a difficult research topic, the included papers mostly have small samples, which makes it difficult to draw strong conclusions for the general population worldwide.

4. Clinical Implications

This work has important implications for all settings of paediatric palliative and bereavement care (hospital, community, advocacy). Our findings allow us to acknowledge that there is still a significant lack of availability of PPC and especially bereavement care services worldwide.

The implementation of standardised specialist bereavement care programmes and the strengthening of available PPC services at hospital, national and international levels are needed. As we noted in our first paper, even when services are available, it is important to assess the quality of care they provide to children and families, and doing this at the hospital level can be a first step.

Implementation strategies should consider early intervention and appropriate follow-up of PPC and bereavement care, considering family's needs and different cultural backgrounds. As we emphasise in paper three, understanding the coping strategies parents adopt after the loss of their child can help health systems and HCPs to offer better support and design appropriate programmes. Effective communication and training/education are key to achieving this, as is raising awareness of the topic.

4.1 Education-training and Communication that crosses borders.

We found that HCPs reported a need for more education and training. The development of new educational programmes for HCPs and community support groups is essential to provide high quality care. Involving not only 'palliative care specialists' but also other HCPs in these educational programmes can increase the coverage of care. Training in communication roles between teams and with patients and families is also crucial, both in the early stages of care and in bereavement follow-up. Research has shown that families who received bereavement support (which involves good communication skills), including anticipatory grief support, coped better with their grief after the child's death.^{85,97}

In this context, active listening and showing compassion to those in difficult circumstances are key to building stronger relationships.¹⁰⁶ Standardised international guidelines for palliative and bereavement care recommend that families who have lost a loved one should have at least one meaningful interaction with a healthcare professional.⁹⁹ We recommend following these guidelines, but considering that multiple contacts over time and not only one interaction, would be beneficial for bereaved families. For example, by increasing the provision and creating a variety of support tools (telephone calls, letters, visits, invitations to the hospital for a memorial day, sibling camps) during the follow-up period may help families to cope with this stage of their lives. As grief is also unique in its duration, it is also recommended that contact with bereaved families be maintained for a longer period (than the usual 1-2 years) to support them in their new process.⁹⁸ This may also be a way of identifying red flags for negative health outcomes. To address the former suggestions, the establishment of a bereavement coordinator position in hospitals should be considered.

4.2 Awareness and Advocacy for PPC and bereavement care.

Awareness of bereavement support and PPC is essential to reach all the children and families around the world who are in need of it. First and foremost, adopting the correct definition of PC is fundamental (which might be part of the educational programmes). Although bereavement and end-of-life care is an integral part of PPC, this is not the only connotation. Palliative and bereavement care extends beyond death, to the compassionate support of patients and their families throughout the course of the illness, and when necessary, after the patient's death. With this in mind, it is important to understand that not all children who need PC will die within days or months; some children with life limiting/threatening diseases may take years or even decades to die.

The involvement of experts, international organisations, policy-makers and other stakeholders is necessary to make changes in the structure of health systems at local and government levels.

Recommendations for academic meetings, lectures at universities, organisations, hospitals, foundations, and even political environments could be of support. Promoting the results of our research and the work that still needs to be done in this context can make a difference and build bridges between all sectors. These could help to overcome the several barriers identified in our work and found as well in other studies worldwide (insufficient funding, staffing, training, education, and clinical guidelines).

As highlighted throughout the thesis, paediatric palliative and bereavement care is fundamental in improving the quality of life for children, families, and entire communities. Compassionate care of children and families in need of support is a mission that requires the collaboration of multiple professions and entities. Therefore, last but not least, the involvement of bereaved parents is an indispensable component in raising awareness of the impact of PPC and bereavement care and in supporting the implementation of new bereavement programmes. Finally, collaboration with community-based programmes (from hospital-based) could also broaden additional vital support and follow-up for these families.

5. Recommendations for further research

More research is needed on PPC and bereavement in both HIC and LMIC settings, especially in paediatric specialties other than oncology and neonatology (e.g. infectious, cardiac, pulmonary, and neurodegenerative diseases, and other causes of disability or death such as accidents), where we found more ongoing research.

Further research is also needed on the differences between the coping strategies of parents who have lost their children to different causes (e.g., disease vs. accident), as well as their wishes and needs for care by HCPs, considering cultural and regional backgrounds. Under-represented groups such as fathers, grandparents, and younger siblings should be made more visible, and long-term follow-up research studies are needed. Finally, implementation strategies should be explored to develop bereavement guidelines that could be adopted at the local, national and international levels. In this regard, although international studies are necessary and important, country- or region-specific research could also adequately address the needs of these children and families nationally and worldwide.

5. Conclusion

Paediatric palliative care, including bereavement care, can serve as a supportive umbrella for the needs of patients and families facing life-limiting and life-threatening illness. Its primary aim is to prevent and reduce suffering for patients and families while improving their quality of life. Their involvement should be comprehensive from the early stages of diagnosis and even beyond death. Our findings show that although some forms of PC appear to be available in European paediatric oncology centres, capacity remains insufficient in a third of them, and early care is usually not offered. In addition, bereavement support programmes are limited in this setting, but more concerningly, they are notably scarce in LMICs. This reinforces the fact that PPC and bereavement care need to be strengthened on a global scale.

Raising awareness among HCPs and other stakeholders could help to promote and implement bereavement care programmes. Understanding the coping strategies used by bereaved family members after the loss of their loved child could help to design these programmes and to provide better support while recognising that mothers, fathers, and siblings may express their grief differently and use different coping styles. Finally, our work identifies important barriers to implementing PPC and bereavement care, in line with other studies. More training, staff, funding, and guidelines are needed to overcome those barriers and ensure the best possible care for this vulnerable population.

It is important for HCPs and health systems to acknowledge that PPC and bereavement care are their responsibility. Currently, the majority of deaths occur in hospital settings,^{121,122} and HCPs are usually the first point of contact for bereavement care and for linking bereaved families to community support. Involvement of all sectors and stakeholders is essential to address the current challenges, by building bridges between the academic, clinical practice, and even policy-making settings.

Final Note: *In the writing process I made use of DeepL Write, an AI tool, only to enhance typography, not to create content. The content of this work is mine alone, feedback from other colleagues during the writing process was greatly appreciated.*

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SUPPLEMENTAL MATERIAL

1. List of scientific publications

1.1 First authorship

Pedraza, E. C., Michel, G., Altherr, A., Hendriks, M. J., & De Clercq, E. (2023). Coping strategies in families who lost a child to cancer: A Scoping review. *European Journal of Cancer: Paediatric Oncology*, (1), 100011. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ejcped.2023.100011>

Pedraza, E.C., Raguindin, P.F., Hendriks, M.J., Vokinger, A.K., De Clercq, E., Rüesch, K., Hjorth, L., von Bueren, A.O., Tinner, E.M., Bergstraesser, E., Wiener, L., Michel, G. (2023). Palliative care services in paediatric oncology centres across Europe: A cross-sectional survey. *European Journal of Cancer: Paediatric Oncology*,(2); 100125. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ejcped.2023.100125>

Pedraza, E.C., Vokinger, A.K., Cleves, D., Michel, G., Wrigley, J., Baker, J.N., Garcia-Quintero, X., McNeil, M.J. Bereavement Support for Parents after the Death of a Child in Low- or Middle-Income Countries: a Systematic Review. Accepted. *Under review*.

1.2. Co-authorship

Vokinger, A. K., **Pedraza, E. C.**, De Clercq, E., Tinner, E. M., Bergsträsser, E., & Michel, G. (2023). Leben mit Verlust: Trauerbegleitung nach dem Tod eines Kindes an Krebs: Angebotene Trauerbegleitung, Coping-Strategien und Bedürfnisse von Eltern. *palliative.ch*, (2), 12–18.

Hendriks, M. J., **Pedraza, E. C.**, Tinner, E. M., Bergstraesser, E., & Michel, G. (2020). Wenn ein Kind an Krebs stirbt ... Auswirkungen auf die Eltern und Bedürfnisse für die Palliativ- und Trauerbegleitung in der pädiatrischen Onkologie. *Schweizer Zeitschrift für Onkologie*, (4), 32–34.

1.3 Under Review

De Clercq, E., Vokinger, A.K., **Pedraza, E.C.**, Bueren, A.O., Tinner, E.M., Michel, G. Cooling facilities in pediatric palliative care: A ritual form of mourning? A scoping literature review.

2. List of scientific presentations

2.1 First authorship

Implementing an End-of-Life (EOL) and Hospital Bereavement Program in a Resource-Constrained Latin America Country: A Source Of Light And Compassion (Love) In The Midst Of Cloudy Times. Oral presentation, 55th Congress of the International Society of Paediatric Oncology, SIOG 2023, SIOG : International Society of Paediatric Oncology, Ontario, Canada, 2023

Coping strategies in families who lost a child to cancer: A Scoping review. Oral presentation, SPOG SSPHO Scientific Meeting 2023, Swiss Paediatric Oncology Group, Bern, Switzerland, 2023

Coping strategies in families who lost a child to cancer: A Systematic review. Oral presentation, Research Symposium Health Lucerne, University of Lucerne, Lucerne, Switzerland, 2023

Paediatric Palliative Oncology Across Europe: A Cross-Sectional Survey. Oral presentation, Research Symposium Health Lucerne, University of Lucerne, Lucerne, Switzerland, 2023

Paediatric Palliative Oncology Across Europe: A Cross-Sectional Survey. Poster, 54th Congress of the International Society of Paediatric Oncology, SIOG 2022,, SIOG : International Society of Paediatric Oncology, Barcelona, Spain, 2022

Paediatric palliative care (PPC) services in paediatric oncology centres in Switzerland. Oral presentation, 5th Maruzza International Congress of Paediatric Palliative Care, Maruzza Foundation, Rome, Italy, 2022

Paediatric palliative care (PPC) services in paediatric oncology centres in Switzerland. Oral presentation, SPOG Scientific Meeting, SPOG: Schweizerische Pädiatrische Onkologie Gruppe, Bern, Online, 2022

Paediatric Palliative Oncology Across Switzerland: A Cross-sectional Survey. Oral presentation, National Palliative Care Congress, Palliative.ch (Marina Carobbio Guscetti, President palliative.ch ; Renate Gurtner Vontobel Managing Director palliative.ch), Biel, 2021

Needs, desires and psychosocial outcomes in bereaved parents who lost their child due to cancer. Oral presentation, Swiss Summer Academy in Palliative Care Research, The research network "palliative care research Switzerland" (pcrs), Münchenwiler (Murten), 2021

Palliative Care and Bereavement Services in Paediatric Oncology Institutions across Europe. Poster, Swiss Public Health Conference 2020, The Swiss Society for Public Health, Swiss School of Public Health, University of Lucerne, Online Conference, 2020

Needs, desires, and psychosocial outcomes in bereaved parents who lost their child due to cancer. Oral presentation, Research Seminar in Health Sciences, Department of Health Sciences and Medicine, Lucerne, Switzerland, 2020.

2.2 Co-authorship

To live with loss: bereavement care for parents who lost a child to cancer. Oral presentation, Nationaler Palliative Care Kongress, palliative.ch, Biel, 2023

Beyond the illness: exploring the multifaceted needs of bereaved parents following the death of their child to cancer. Oral presentation, IPOS World Congress, IPOS, Milano, 2023

Les systèmes de refroidissement comme rituel de deuil. Une étude de la Portée. Oral presentation, 10ème congrès du Réseau Francophone de soins palliatifs pédiatriques, Geneva, 2023

Implementación de un programa de atención al duelo en un país en desarrollo de américa latina. Una fuente de luz y compasión (amor) en medio de tiempos nublados. Oral presentation, Brasil, 2023